

Deliverable Report D3.3

Database Tools Development

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¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document	
AJAX	Asynchronous JavaScript and XML
API	Application Programming Interface
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FER	FAIR Enabling Resources
FIC	FAIR Implementation Community
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GURPIs	Globally Unique Resolvable and Persistent Identifiers
IATA	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment
IOP	Impact Outcome Pathway
IP	Intellectual Property
LCA	Lifecycle Assessment
MVVM	Model-View-ViewModel
PBK	Physiologically Based Kinetic
QSAR	Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship
QSPR	Quantitative Structure–Property Relationship
REST	Representational State Transfer
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
SSO	Single-Sign-On
S-LCA	Social Lifecycle Assessment
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.3 - Database Tools Development, documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the INSIGHT Database, which supports the project's integrated Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework. As part of Task 3.3 within Work Package 3 (WP3), the deliverable presents the technical, conceptual, and findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR)-compliance details required for the management of heterogeneous scientific data used for INSIGHT's modelling, assessment, and decision-support workflows.

The database builds upon and extends the nanoPharos infrastructure, developed by NovaM, which is based on the ChEMBL schema, to support advanced materials and chemical substances, multiscale characterisation data, exposure and toxicological evidence, omics data, life-cycle and sustainability indicators, and model-derived outputs. The approach maintains compatibility with existing infrastructures while expanding relational and semantic layers to accommodate INSIGHT-specific requirements such as Integrated Outcome Pathways (IOPs), Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA), mechanistic evidence streams, and multi-domain SSbD criteria.

D3.3 describes the database's architecture, including its relational MySQL foundation, the conceptual model, and the technical choices enabling high-performance data storage, curation, provenance capture, interoperability, and secure access. It outlines how data and metadata are curated, validated, contextualised, and published through automated or semi-automated workflows, supported by templates, provenance tracking, versioning, and FAIR-compliant machine-actionable formats. A detailed description is provided for the user interface, backend/frontend integration, submission pipelines, and the role of Keycloak in access control and data governance.

The report further explains how the database operationalises the FAIR principles across findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. This includes the use of globally unique, persistent, and resolvable identifiers, extensive bibliographic, scientific, and provenance metadata, and the publication of machine-actionable metadata records through nanodash and Zenodo.

The processing and FAIRification of INSIGHT's data provides a unified structure that can link materials, batches, experiments, models, LCA/S-LCA indicators, and decision-relevant outputs. It acts as a foundational component for the INSIGHT Knowledge Graph, supporting semantic reasoning, cross-domain interoperability, and evidence integration. As such, D3.3 not only provides a technical overview of the database implementation but sets the basis for downstream activities in WP3 (FAIRification and Knowledge Graph development), supports modelling pipelines in WP2, impact assessment workflows in WP4, and GUI and decision-support development in WP5.

I Introduction

Deliverable D3.3 describes the development and deployment of the INSIGHT Database, which constitutes the core data infrastructure supporting the project's integrated Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) assessment framework. The deliverable defines the conceptual basis, scope, and structural requirements of the database and explains how the data model supports FAIR data management, cross-domain interoperability, downstream modelling and decision-support processes within INSIGHT. As part of WP3, D3.3 lays the foundation for the project's Knowledge Graph, model integration workflows, and evidence-based SSbD methodology, which will be integrated and/or supported by the database.

D3.3 documents the architecture, structure, and intended function of the INSIGHT database. It describes how the database structures and harmonises heterogeneous data sources across the project, which range from physicochemical characterisation to toxicity, exposure, omics, lifecycle analysis (LCA), social LCA (S-LCA), physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modelling, Quantitative Structure–Activity/Property Relationship (QSAR/QSPR), and model-derived indicators, and organises them within a ChEMBL-based data schema using clearly defined FAIR-compliant workflows.

Beyond the technical description of the database's schema, the deliverable explains its role as an enabling component for the INSIGHT Knowledge Graph, which provides semantic interoperability and cross-domain reasoning capabilities, and for the SSbD framework, which depends on structured, traceable, high-quality (meta)data. Therefore, D3.3 is not only a technical reference for the INSIGHT database, but a broader guide for external alignment for scientific, regulatory, and sustainability stakeholders.

As a result, D3.3, covers the conceptual and technical design of the INSIGHT database, including:

- the relational data model and its alignment with existing infrastructures;
- the semantic extensions required for Integrated Outcome Pathways (IOPs), (S-)LCA, and SSbD assessment;
- the mechanisms for provenance, uncertainty, and annotation;
- the graph-based representation that underpins the under-development Knowledge Graph and cross-domain information flows;
- the upcoming interfaces and linkages between data, computational models, and decision-support tools.

The focus of D3.3 is the model and architecture, not the full population or operational deployment of the database. Data ingestion and FAIRification activities will continue throughout the project, and their implementation is captured in deliverables D3.4 and D3.5. In any case, the INSIGHT database supports the project's overarching objective to deliver an evidence-based, multi-criteria SSbD methodology that integrates scientific, sustainability, and societal considerations into transparent decision processes. As the central data infrastructure, it connects and consolidates the evidence streams generated across the entire consortium and respective WPs underpinning cross-WP integration by ensuring that all evidence, regardless of origin or format, is stored and represented in a consistent, interoperable, and machine-readable manner.

2 System architecture and conceptual design

2.1 Architectural rationale

The INSIGHT database serves as a comprehensive and FAIR Supporting Resource (FSR) capable of supporting the full range of scientific, mechanistic, and sustainability data required for SSbD assessment. The design responds to the SSbD challenge of collating data relevant to health, environment, social impacts, and economic performance, which are fragmented across diverse sources, sourced from

different partners, and generated using heterogeneous methodologies. To enable genuine integration across these domains, the project requires a unified (meta)data management system that is structurally robust, semantically interoperable, and operationally flexible.

The INSIGHT database architectural approach follows that of the nanoPharos database, which is based on the extension of the ChEMBL schema (Figure 1) to accommodate materials (meta)data. At its core, the ChEMBL database includes 3 primary pillars, i.e., molecular entities, assays, and activities expressed through its respective database schema (2). Molecular entities correspond to chemical structures and physicochemical properties, Assays represent biological or biochemical experimental processes, and Activities record the respective bioactivity endpoints. Similarly, the INSIGHT database inherits this relational structure and follows the same relational logic. In the INSIGHT case, the Molecule entity is replaced with the Material one, which are now sub-entities of a super entity, i.e., Substance. Furthermore, data provenance is expressed using rich provenance and bibliographic metadata. These metadata are catalogued as an overarching entity for the documents and/or references and datasets for both the ChEMBL and INSIGHT schemas. Other adaptations of the ChEMBL schema include the extension of the Structure entity to include the unique identifiers of advanced materials, the expansion of the physicochemical properties to accommodate materials characterisation, as well as the introduction of a scientific metadata layer to capture all relevant information for FAIRification and transparency purposes.

The INSIGHT database also includes the concept of “batch”, which links each material with information regarding production, shipment, and usage of a specific material under different contexts. This is linked with specific information regarding the material’s composition, e.g., doping, surface modifications, and its crystallographic information. The materials characterisation part includes the potential for both experimental and computational data. Exposure Scenario extends ChEMBL’s Assay entity with materials-related experimental workflows and requirements, e.g., exposure route, exposure duration, medium in which the materials are dispersed, and their respective concentration. These feed directly into the Target and Activity entities, which generalise, for materials, ChEMBL’s respective entities. In this way, the INSIGHT database preserves the current ChEMBL relational structure with equivalencies and extends the sub-entities and categories with material-specific information.

In more detail, to maximise the information, analytical potential, and added value of the INSIGHT datasets, a detailed data model has been developed to align with project requirements. The data model describes the links and dependencies between the different types of data produced in INSIGHT along with their respective metadata. The data model is based on a detailed description of the material of interest, starting from the atomic level, i.e., unit cell and crystallographic information for materials, and builds up to macroscopic information, i.e., physicochemical and surface chemistry characterisation.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the Pharos solution, which is the basis of the INSIGHT database and is based on the extension of the ChEMBL data schema for the management chemicals and materials (meta)data. Blue: Introduced or modified ChEMBL entities bridging or expanding the ChEMBL schema to accommodate materials data; Light blue: original ChEMBL schema; Green: nanoPharos schema. Image re-printed from (1).

The materials or chemicals effects are also described using different data types, e.g., *in vitro* toxicity targeting a range of endpoints (cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, immunotoxicity, developmental toxicity, etc.), AOPs, and ecotoxicity (e.g., materials effects on daphnids, earthworms, fish etc.). The exposure and release routes, e.g., environmental compartments, binding to soils, road dust etc., are catalogued as part of the metadata to facilitate data provenance and context, FAIRification, and the development

of meaningful metadata records. At the same time, these metadata are also available as covariates for meta-analysis and data-driven modelling development when combining data from heterogeneous studies.

This approach reflects the reality that the border between data and metadata is fluid, and that the metadata of one study can become the data of another, and thus allows the translation of the captured (meta)data into Scientific Knowledge Graphs, along with the data it describes, which allows for the visualisation of data flows and interconnections, defines the required metadata, and enables exploration and understanding of the connections between data originating from diverse sources (3). Users are then able to better understand the data model functionality and how a specific material or chemical, organism, endpoint, or other factor has been used in different studies and its impact on the respective outcomes, without having to rely on complex schema documentation.

One of the key implementations is the need to address the complexity of novel and advanced materials, as well as issues related to differences in storage and exposure to different environments leading to different transformations (4, 5). The INSIGHT database manages this by defining different batches or altered forms of a “parent” material, i.e., the original as-produced material before any characterisation or assays have been performed. The database uses a series of identifiers to catalogue the imported materials like the Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) number, EC number, International Uniform Chemical Information Database (IUCLID), Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES) representation, InChi and its extension to NMs, via the InChI which describes the “parent” or ideal composition of a material (6).

The structural information of a material can be based either on bibliographical data, e.g., from the Materials Project website containing information on 178,627 materials (7), or on experimental data if researchers use e.g., high-quality XRD data and Rietveld refinement to recreate their NM’s unit cell and calculate the respective information (8). At the same time, computational representations of specific materials have been developed, which can be used for the calculation of atomistic descriptors using simulations and physics-based modelling to enrich experimental datasets. Thus, molecular and periodic table-based descriptors have been included in nanoPharos, including metal electronegativity, atomic and ionic radius etc. This has led to a total of 119 materials-related descriptors that can be used to describe a material. These comprise of 36 physicochemical descriptors (including 18 that can be extracted from TEM images using NovaM’s NanoXtract tool (9, 10)), 3 structural descriptors, 18 molecular and periodic table-based descriptors and 62 atomistic descriptors (Table 1). The flexibility and scalability of the database allows the extension of these descriptors based on emerging and evolving project needs.

Table 1. Physicochemical, molecular, and atomistic descriptors available in the nanoPharos and the INSIGHT database.

#	Name
1	Morphology
2	Core size
3	Nominal width/diameter
4	Nanomaterial length (major axis)
5	Nanomaterial width (minor axis)
6	Size distribution
7	Specific surface area
8	Estimated specific surface area
9	Geometric surface area
10	Hydrodynamic size

11	ζ-potential
12	Point of zero ζ-potential (iso-electric point)
13	Ageing
14	No. of walls (for nanotubes)
15	Polydispersity index in exposure medium
16	Coating
17	Functionalisation
18	Purity
TEM images-based descriptors	
19	Circularity
20	Perimeter [nm]
21	Convexity
22	Extend
23	Diameter [nm]
24	Area [nm ²]
25	Circularity #2
26	Convexity #2
27	Eccentricity
28	Main Elongation
29	Minimum Ferets Diameter [nm]
30	Maximum Ferets Diameter [nm]
31	Major Axis [nm]
32	Minor Axis [nm]
33	Boundary Size [nm]
34	Boxivity
35	Roundness
36	Solidity
Structural descriptors	
37	Space group
38	Unit cell angles (α , β , γ)
39	Unit cell dimensions (a, b, c)
Molecular descriptors	
40	Atomic radius
41	Atomic weight
42	Charge
43	Conduction band energy
44	Electronegativity
45	Energy band gap
46	Energy based on enthalpy of formation

47	Ionic radius
48	Me _x O _y absolute electronegativity
49	Molecular weight
50	Periodic table group
51	Periodic table period
52	Standard enthalpy of formation
53	Sum of metal electronegativity
54	Sum of metal electronegativity to oxygen atoms
55	Total number of metal atoms
56	Total number of oxygen atoms
57	Valence band energy
Atomistic (computational) descriptors	
58	Log of total No. of atoms in NP
59	Log of total No. of atoms in core region of NP
60	Log of total No. of atoms in surface region of NP
61	Log of total No. of Me atoms in NP
62	Log of total No. of Me atoms in core region of NP
63	Log of total No. of Me atoms in surface region of NP
64	Log of total No. of O atoms in NP
65	Log of total No. of O atoms in core region of NP
66	Log of total No. of O atoms in surface region of NP
67	Average pot. energy of all atoms in NP in eV
68	Average pot. energy of atoms in core region of NP in eV
69	Average pot. energy of atoms in surface region of NP in eV
70	Relative Average pot. energy of Me atoms in NP in eV
71	Relative Average pot. energy of Me atoms in core region of NP in eV
72	Relative Average pot. energy of Me atoms in surface region of NP in eV
73	Relative Average pot. energy of O atoms in NP in eV
74	Relative Average pot. energy of O atoms in core region of NP in eV
75	Relative Average pot. energy of O atoms in surface region of NP in e
76	Average coordination No. of all atoms in NP
77	Average coordination No. of atoms in core region of NP
78	Average coordination No. of atoms in surface region of NP
79	Average coordination No. of Me atoms in NP
80	Average coordination No. of Me atoms in core region of NP
81	Average coordination No. of Me atoms in surface region of N
82	Average coordination No. of O atoms in NP
83	Average coordination No. of O atoms in core region of NP
84	Average coordination No. of O atoms in surface region of NP

85	Diameter of the NP in Å
86	Surface area of the NP in Å ²
87	Volume of the NP in Å ³
88	Lattice energy of NP in eV
89	Relative lattice energy of NP to bulk material (eV)
90	Lattice energy of NP divided by the diameter of NP
91	Lattice energy of NP per unit surface area
92	Lattice energy of NP per unit volume
93	Average length of force vector for all atoms
94	Average length of force vector for all atoms in core region
95	Average length of force vector for all atoms in surface region
96	Average length of force vector for all Me atoms
97	Average length of force vector for Me atoms in core region
98	Average length of force vector for Me atoms in surface region
99	Average length of force vector for all O atoms
100	Average length of force vector for O atoms in core region
101	Average length of force vector for O atoms in surface region
102	Average length of force vector surface normal component for all atoms
103	Average length of force vector surface normal component for all atoms in core region
104	Average length of force vector surface normal component for all atoms in surface region
105	Average length of force vector surface normal component for all Me atoms
106	Average length of force vector surface normal component for Me atoms in core region
107	Average length of force vector surface normal component for Me atoms in surface region
108	Average length of force vector surface normal component for all O atoms
109	Average length of force vector surface normal component for O atoms in core region
110	Average length of force vector surface normal component for O atoms in surface region
111	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for all atoms
112	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for all atoms in core region

11 3	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for all atoms in surface region
11 4	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for all Me atoms
11 5	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for Me atoms in core region
11 6	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for Me atoms in surface region
11 7	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for all O atoms
11 8	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for O atoms in core region
11 9	Average length of force vector surface tangent component for O atoms in surface region

The exposure, interactions, hazard and risk assessment part of nanoPharos allows users to upload and import relevant data along with methodological assay-related information as part of the metadata. In this case, metadata are also handled as data points since methodological assay information have been found to play a statistically significant role during meta-analyses (11) and ML model development (12), especially in cases where data from different sources and different methodological approaches have been combined. For this reason, the INSIGHT database, through nanoPharos, has been designed to enable methodological fields to be used as variables or covariates during meta-analyses and ML development across heterogeneous studies, e.g., the cytotoxicity assay type as different cellular toxicity assays measure different aspects of cell death and thus assay differences may explain more of the variability in a dataset. Thus, the database offers users the opportunity to import data on the biological entities and/or biological entities categories tested and the assay type, along with respective information on the experimental setup and end-points used.

Furthermore, the data imported into the INSIGHT database are directly linked to their respective metadata. In this way, each data point is linked to information describing how it was produced, who produced and curated that data, who owns the data, the license under which a dataset is available, any relevant publications, and more. Three types of metadata are accommodated to satisfy the FAIR Data Principles requirements for rich metadata for findability (FAIR Data Principle F2) and reusability (FAIR Data Principle R1):

- Bibliographic metadata: dataset title, description, owner(s), contact detail(s), relevant publications, unique IDs and descriptors, e.g., DOI, ORCID, file type and size.
- Provenance metadata: data producer(s), curator(s), methods used to produce the data, date of data production, date of modification (where applicable), versioning.
- Scientific metadata: protocols, methods, instruments used, analytical and computational algorithms, software used and versions.

Combining these, a relational database schema has been developed, which is compliant with the FAIR Data principles, and maps the complex relationships and dependencies in materials and chemicals safety data. Key elements of the schema include entity-relationship diagrams, precise data types, constraints to ensure data integrity, and indexes for optimised query performance. This approach allows for the development of a scalable database, the data model of which can be extended based on specific requirements leading to the integration of different data types and respective metadata management. This hybrid design ensures that detailed experimental datasets, computational model outputs, mechanistic pathways, and life cycle indicators can be expressed in a harmonised format while also being connected through machine-interpretable semantic relationships. The system is specifically

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designed to support INSIGHT's IOP framework and the SSbD decision workflows built in WP4 and WP5.

2.2 Logical and physical design foundations

The INSIGHT database is based on MySQL, which is the underlying relational database management system of nanoPharos. The benefit of relational databases, like MySQL, over other non-relational solutions, e.g., NoSQL, is that they can better handle predefined schemas for the management of structured data used for the development of data-driven workflows. Non-relational databases, on the other hand, are better at handling unstructured or dynamic data. Another advantage of relational databases is that they are table-based, i.e., can better accommodate scientific datasets, while non-relational ones are better for documents and graph databases.

As a result, MySQL provides databases, including the INSIGHT database, with increased performance and scalability, compared to non-relational ones, which leads to better web-based performance regarding data retrieval and transaction rate speeds. This streamlines the management of multiple simultaneous queries. As an open-source system, MySQL is a cost-efficient solution allowing for better budget allocation towards more complex feature and tool development. MySQL is easy to setup, maintain, and customise, it is compatible with multiple operating systems and platforms, and has extensive community support making it easy to debug. This ensures an easily maintainable high stability and security level, which is particularly important when handling sensitive data. MySQL provides readily available features like encrypted connections and data-at-rest encryption options.

Database development employed a set of tools and technologies that ensure functionality robustness, scalability, and back and forward compatibility, as well as industry-standard database performance. Database development has been based on Java, JavaScript, and HTML5. Java has been used for backend development, as it offers robust and platform-independent features, while its Application Programming Interface (API) allows the streamlined handling of complex tasks and operations (13). The database's backend system management is supported by Wildfly, which is a scalable and modular open-source application server that offers quick initialisation and efficient resource management for high performance and responsiveness.

On the frontend, JavaScript and HTML5 offer a flexible and friendly user-experience through real-time user interface (UI) interactions. These are enhanced by CSS3, which improves the user experience using advanced styling, aesthetic, and user-friendly solutions in the graphical user interface (GUI), without loss in functionality. Synchronisation of the backend with the frontend, for a seamless user experience, is performed using the ZK Framework. The ZK Framework is used to manage AJAX (Asynchronous JavaScript and XML) and JavaScript operations during UI development and is used during the development of Rich Internet Applications (14). The use of the ZK Framework reduces complexity and ensures a smooth and reliable user experience and an advanced and fully responsive GUI design.

The ZK Framework enables Rich Internet Applications using a server-centric model that offloads complex data processing to the server side, reducing client-side scripting. Its extensive suite of AJAX components automatically handles UI updates for dynamic, real-time interfaces, while the Model-View-ViewModel (MVVM) design pattern separates data logic from the UI to enhance maintainability and scalability. Additionally, ZK's event-driven programming paradigm further streamlines application responsiveness by simplifying the synchronization of UI interactions. Integrating CSS with the ZK Framework, the database offers a user-friendly interface that balances functionality and aesthetics.

Data security and access control is managed using Keycloak to set up authentication and authorisation protocols. The identity and access management processes support role and privileges assignment, so that different users, e.g., database managers, curators, data re-users, are offered different functionalities and views. Keycloak provides increased security through user authentication and supports Single-Sign-On (SSO) and user federation functions. Keycloak ensures sensitive data protection, in accordance

with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), restricting access to users based on their assigned roles and rights.

2.3 User interface

Based on the database’s design and development described in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 and the respective data model, the UI was designed to be task-oriented, role-specific, and aligned to the underlying database schema and its focus on delivering ready-for-modelling datasets. For this reason, the design principles of the UI are focussed on the development of customised, case-specific datasets by choosing the materials and/or assay descriptors, i.e., data and metadata, of interest for specific materials from those included and available in the database.

The [landing page](#) of the database (Figure 2) guides users to the advanced configuration section, and not the general keyword search, where they can choose from the available (meta)data tables, attributes, and values. A side panel displays clickable boxes for selecting tables, while dropdowns, radio buttons, and an output configuration option allow users to define and refine their searches according to logical operators, equality, or inequality. In this way, users can include or exclude attributes, move them between lists, and apply additional filters. Furthermore, dedicated search boxes enhance navigation, and the ability to click on radio buttons to choose inequality options, e.g., “Greater” or “Lesser” or “Equal”, enables data retrieval based on specific user needs. The system then exports the refined results in a clearly presented tabular format, supporting efficient and targeted data exploration and direct import into computational workflows.

Figure 2. In the Advanced Search Configuration Page users can pick the data and respective tables of interest from the complete set in the database. Users can choose multiple tables and switch between them using radio buttons (see top left black rectangle). Users can also define and refine their searches according to logical operators, equality, or inequality (bottom left).

Considering the evolving data production, processing, and exploitation processes of the INSIGHT project, the database has provisions for embargoed and sensitive data, which may be locked and is thus inaccessible to general users. For this, Keycloak is being employed and specific permissions and privileges are applied on a case-by-case basis. When logging in to access sensitive data, users are redirected to the nanoPharos database management system, where 4 options are available (where applicable based on specific privileges):

- Embargoed/Locked or Project-specific Data
- Bulk Insert
- Single Insert/Modify
- Table Configuration

Users that belong to a specific user-group are able to see data that may be under embargo, i.e., to be released based on data owner exploitation or following expiration of the embargo period, or data that are locked due to sensitivity, e.g., personal data, commercially sensitive data. The data that are visible to specific users is defined based on rules defined by each individual contributor and are addressed individually.

For data curation, the Bulk Insert option (Figure 3) allows data providers / database curators to upload data using templates developed for each parameter. The users use a dropdown menu to pick the metric they want to upload (Figure 3 top) and the system provides them with the option to download the preformatted template in CSV (Comma Separated Values) format. The users fill in the template, upload it, and the system automatically links the template columns with the respective database ones (Figure 3 bottom).

Figure 3. Bulk Insert Data menu page (top) and Data Upload and validation (bottom).

Curators can use their own templates also, but they will then have to manually map the CSV file they upload to the required database attributes (Figure 4). In this case, the curators would see the image presented in Figure 4 (top) and would need to click on the Select button (see black rectangle under Edit) for the respective row and chose the matching column from their uploaded template (Figure 4 middle), e.g., CAS Number in this example is mapped to CAS, which is required in the database, and press the Add and then confirm buttons (see black rectangle in Figure 4 middle). Repeating the procedure for all relevant columns, curators can quickly and easily map an entire template to nanoPharos (Figure 4 bottom) and upload it. The users will also need to define, where applicable, the unit(s) of their data. These will automatically be converted to the default units used in the database for the specific descriptor.

Figure 4. Users using their own templates (instead of those provided by the database) will need to manually map the columns in their templates to the database-specific attributes before uploading their dataset to the database.

At the same time, curators need to import the required metadata for transparency, reproducibility, data quality, and FAIRification purposes. Using the specialised templates provided by the database, curators define the required basic technical, descriptor specific, provenance, and bibliographic metadata. In this way, database managers and administrators can access the necessary information to ensure that data are published (or not) and to develop the machine-actionable metadata templates in nanodash. As soon as a template is submitted the system checks that the provided (meta)data meet the necessary type and format requirements (Figure 5) and if the quality check is passed the (meta)data are imported. (Meta)data are linked together using their unique identifiers to create a combined dataset. Prior to publication internal checks are performed regarding the licensing and data ownership. Based on the submission, either the entire dataset, or a summary of the metadata is published., i.e.,

title, summary, type, and nanodash template. The datasets are also transformed into machine-actionable JSON and XML templates.

Figure 5. Schematic workflow for (meta)data publication in the INSIGHT database.

To add or modify single entries (Figure 6), the Single Insert/Modify menu offers curators the ability to choose a specific table and perform the desired action. They can manually add attributes, while the system provides information on the data type required for each field. Built-in quality control scripts verify correct formatting and check for missing mandatory fields. To modify data, curators pick a table, select attributes to update, and retrieve existing values for specific entry IDs, which can then be edited or removed. Each successful action triggers a confirmation message, helping maintain transparent and reliable record-keeping throughout the curation process.

Single Insert/Modify

Select table
 ▼

Available operations
 ▼

concentration Insert

DB Table	Data Type	Value	Units
Concentration ID	Integer	<input type="text"/>	*
Element	String	<input type="text" value="Ag"/>	
Value	Float	<input type="text" value="5"/>	
Standard Deviation	Float	<input type="text" value="0.5"/>	
Basic Technical Metadata ID	Integer	<input type="text" value="1"/> <input type="button" value="Search"/>	

Single Insert/Modify

Select table
 ▼

Available operations
 ▼

Search by:
 ▼ Concentration_ID =

concentration Modify

DB Table	Data Type	Value	Units
Concentration ID	Integer	<input type="text" value="2"/>	*
Element	String	<input type="text" value="Ag"/>	
Value	Float	<input type="text" value="5"/>	
Standard Deviation	Float	<input type="text" value="0.5"/>	
Basic Technical Metadata ID	Integer	<input type="text"/> <input type="button" value="Search"/>	

Figure 6. The single insert (top) and modify (bottom) pages allow curators to manually input or modify existing (meta)data. The system provides information on the allowed data type for each field. Required fields are marked with a red star. Full documentation of changes is recorded for versioning and provenance tracking.

Database managers and administrators can access the Table Configuration and Table Attribute Configuration pages (Figure 7). The Table Configuration feature (Figure 7, top) lets database managers or administrators control how each table appears and the required information. Through this functionality, the tables can be renamed, its visibility changed (e.g., to decrease findability or remove if it is not required in a specific database instance), and descriptions added to aid Findability. Security features prevent duplicate names to avoid confusion. Through the Change Table Attributes option (Figure 7, bottom), table attributes can be renamed or changed (e.g., for technical or developing purposes), their visibility defined, and descriptive details or indicative values can be provided. When any changes made through these pages are implemented, any other components in the specific dataset / database instance containing these tables, e.g., Advanced Search and Output Configuration, are automatically updated to maintain a consistent, bug-free, and user-friendly environment.

Table Configuration

Change Table Attributes

Table Configuration

Table Names:
 ▼

Display Name:

Visibility:
 Not Visible

Description:

Representative Columns:

Table Attribute Configuration

Change Tables

Table Attribute Configuration

Table Names:
 ▼

Attribute Names:
 ▼

Display Attribute Name:

Visibility:
 Not Visible

Attribute Description:

Example Value:

Figure 7. The Table Configuration (top) and the Table Attribute Configuration (bottom) pages.

2.4 INSIGHT data

INSIGHT will gather, curate, and upload data across its case studies to populate the INSIGHT database and knowledge graph. These will include a comprehensive, multi-modal set of FAIR data covering intrinsic properties, mechanistic biological responses, exposure and fate, life-cycle inventories, social indicators, and predictive modelling outputs for INSIGHT's planned case studies. These include PFAS, graphene-based materials, antimicrobial coatings, and amorphous silica and data will be uploaded as and when they are produced by the respective partners. These include a diverse set of physicochemical, toxicity, exposure, fate, omics, LCA, S-LCA, PBK, QSAR, and manufacturing data, originating from literature, industrial partners, and research institutions. Together, these datasets map the full chain from material identity through impact pathways, supporting the population of the INSIGHT Data Graph and downstream integration with the Model Graph and Impact Outcome Pathways.

Data production is ongoing and around 63 unique datasets (134 data files) covering a broad range of materials and impact domains have been produced. More data will be generated during the project or extracted from the LCA/S-LCA pipelines and modelling activities. A detailed data reporting will take place in D3.2 – Report on the FAIRification of datasets (M36).

2.4.1 PFAS case study

For PFAS, the database will integrate datasets describing the supply chain, environmental emissions, physicochemical properties, biological activity, omics responses, and predictive modelling outputs. Detailed supply-chain and product-use information, docking, omics, and toxicological and exposure data will be harvested and curated from existing literature, the project, modelling. Dose-response and PBK-ready parameters will also be included.

2.4.2 Graphene case study

For graphene-based materials, manufacturing and material characterisation information including particle size distribution, elemental composition, up-conversion rates, defect density, and other key physicochemical parameters will be gathered within INSIGHT. Toxicological, exposure, fate, and omics datasets are already being pre-processed. Mechanical and structural data relevant for use in construction and energy applications have been curated from literature and will be included in the database.

2.4.3 Antimicrobial materials case study

The antimicrobial case study will include data on toxicity and ecotoxicity of UV-C up-conversion / up-converted UV-C irradiation- (31), metal-oxide- and radical-generating surfaces (SEM, FIB-SEM, fibroblast assays, keratinocyte assays, OECD skin irritation and sensitisation). Exposure and release data are limited but will be supplemented through INTEGRA modelling and supporting literature. Physicochemical features (composition, size, morphology) will be uploaded as they become available.

2.4.4 Amorphous silica case study

Silica datasets will include existing LCA, S-LCA, and toxicological information. This includes product-specific physicochemical data, release behaviour, supply-chain attributes, omics, and literature-derived PBK data (e.g., SAS PBK model). Comparative LCA from published studies will also be indexed.

2.4.5 Modelling-derived data

Modelling outputs that generate structured, reusable datasets like exposure estimates, internal dose predictions, docking scores for PFAS, protein interactions, QSAR input features and predictions, and PBK simulation parameters will also be integrated into the data graph.

3 INSIGHT and FAIR data

The INSIGHT database, based on the nanoPharos solution, is a data registry, which is increasingly compliant with the FAIR Data Principles (15) and applies the Scientific FAIR Data Principles (16) to facilitate use by non-technical data producers. The FAIRness implementation underpinning nanoPharos is based on the GO FAIR Foundation interpretation of the FAIR Data Principles (17). The database's FAIRness degree can be monitored and assessed using the nanoPharos's FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) (18), using the FIP Wizard (19), where the respective FAIR implementation choices are catalogued. A FIP presents the choices made by a specific FAIR Implementation Community (FIC) for maximising the FAIRness level of their (meta)data (20). Comparison of this FIP with those of other FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) or FICs can be achieved via a FAIR Convergence Matrix (21). This matrix can be used to track the FAIR landscape between similar FICs, identify opportunities for optimisation around reuse and interoperability, and promote harmonisation between the FICs (20).

3.1 Findability

Data findability is based on the assignment of unique identifiers (FAIR Data Principle F1) based on the RFC 3986 IETF standard for Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) (22). Similarly, metadata are published as a nanopublication using nanodash (FAIR Data Principle F4) (23). In this way, the metadata record becomes a digital resource, receives a Globally Unique Persistent, and Resolvable Identifier (GUPRI, FAIR Data Principle F1), and becomes human and machine findable via searchable indexes like nanodash and Zenodo (FAIR Data Principle F4). (Meta)data publications contain the other's GUPRI referencing each other (FAIR Data Principle F3). For each dataset published, a respective publication is created in Zenodo (24) containing the dataset's title, summary, GUPRI of (meta)data, license, and contributors. Through Zenodo and by adding the funding information, the datasets are also indexed in OpenAIRE (25) and linked to INSIGHT. In this way, the (meta)data are indexed in various searchable resources, i.e., nanoPharos, nanodash, Zenodo, and OpenAIRE (FAIR Data Principle F4).

Data findability is supported using rich metadata (FAIR Data Principle F1) from the three categories described in the section 2.1, i.e., bibliographic, provenance, and scientific metadata. For Findability the definition of metadata corresponds to descriptive metadata that allows humans and machines to identify a resource of interest through querying, searching, or filtering (17). This means that datasets are accompanied by information like title, summary or abstract, creator, owner, license, unique identifiers, publication data, publisher, keywords, etc. Defining "rich" for metadata is not a straightforward process and is usually left to the respective scientific communities to define it. "Rich", for the purposes of FAIR Data Principle F2, corresponds to the datasets being described with the following bibliographic and provenance metadata:

- Unique identifier of the dataset in the form of a URI or DOI
- Title
- Summary/Abstract
- Data creators/producers, curators, owners (identified via ORCID IDs or another personal unique identifier)
- Access license
- Date created and published
- Dataset version
- File type and size
- Relevant publications describing or utilising the dataset (identified using DOIs or other unique ID)

The (meta)data, including the scientific metadata that fall mainly under FAIR Data Principle R1, are linked based on the database's underlying schema, which is based on that of the ChEMBL database (2).

3.2 Accessibility

Accessibility is offered either through the web-human interface (26), or remotely using a Representational State Transfer (REST) API (27). The REST API offers users the ability to retrieve datasets using their database identifier, as well as enabling programmatic interaction with other databases or modelling tools (FAIR Data Principle A1). As per the FAIR Data Principle A1.1 the API is open, freely accessible, and universally implementable (27), although it does not currently support authentication and authorisation procedures (FAIR Data Principle A1.2) to access, for example, sensitive or embargoed data. The API also does not, currently, support retrieval based on keywords and there is no integration of search based on ontological terms.

For metadata longevity (FAIR Data Principle A2), we have opted to publish machine-actionable metadata records in nanodash (23) and Zenodo (24), as described in the Findability section. Publication in these platforms ensures that even if the data are no longer available, the metadata records will remain for the long-term. Thus, if a dataset has been used and referenced in a published resource, the metadata record will persist and provide a description to sufficiently understand the data's nature, content, and provenance (17).

3.3 Interoperability

FAIR Data Principle II requires that the (meta)data are annotated using established structured ontologies or vocabularies. Currently, the nanoPharos datasets are available in machine-actionable forms like JSON and XML. The metadata, in nanodash, can be accessed in machine-actionable forms like TriG, JSON-LD, N-Quads, and XML (FAIR data principle II). nanodash requires the use of annotated terms in compliance with the FAIR Data Principle II, as all terms are annotated using established ontologies like the eNanoMapper Ontology (eNMO) (28), the Nanoparticle Ontology (NPO) (29), Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI) (30), and more, which follow the FAIR Data Principles (FAIR Data Principle I2) and have been mapped in the I-ADOPT Ontology Framework used in nanodash. Nevertheless, further alignment and coverage with the SSbD dimensions, e.g., LCA, S-LCA, safety, and advanced materials, which provide a common conceptual framework that strengthens cross-domain linkage and improves the consistency of annotations within the database is required and are currently under development in WP4. Furthermore, the INSIGHT method and model annotation schema will be integrated into the interoperability layer, enabling more precise characterisation of model assumptions, applicability domains, and methodological relationships.

FAIR Data Principle I3 requires that (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data. This is applied in the database as part of the provenance or bibliographical metadata. Key examples include (meta)data versioning, where the latest files include references to the previous versions as well as a record of the changes made. Curated datasets include the references, in the form of DOIs, of the original data sources and, where applicable, the DOIs of publications related to specific datasets are included in the metadata records.

3.4 Reusability

While FAIR data principle F2 aims to facilitate (meta)data findability, R1 corresponds to the core of the (meta)data and whether they are applicable for the intended reuse. In practice, FAIR data principle R1 refers to the scientific (meta)data. Each data point can be linked to a wide range of metadata. These include the methods, protocols, or assays used to produce them, different experiments linked to a specific material, distinct batches of a material and respective physicochemical characterisations and assays, computational descriptors, and more.

(Meta)data availability is clearly defined via licensing. The default nanoPharos license is CC-BY-4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International), although data owners can apply their preferred license based on specific requirements, e.g., embargoed, sensitive data. The licenses are complemented with detailed provenance metadata (FAIR data principle R1.2), as described for FAIR data principles F2 and R1, which are publicly available. In this way, (re)users can identify any changes made to the datasets,

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when they were produced, the data owners (data ownership remains with the data producers or curators for literature data and is not transferred to NovaM), the required credit (license information), data processing methods applied, and more. All this information is based on continuous consultation with domain experts and is updated, expanded, and refined as projects and materials science in general evolve (FAIR data principle R1.3).

It must be noted here, that reusability within INSIGHT extends beyond the traditional FAIR meaning and interpretations of enabling data to be accessed and reused in new contexts. Within INSIGHT, reuse is also linked to the integration of all curated and harmonised data into the Impact Knowledge Graph, where it becomes part of the project's semantically connected ecosystem, which supports mechanistic interpretation, cross-domain assessment, and computational inference. Once incorporated into the Knowledge Graph, the same datasets can be reused by the model pipelines in WP4 and the SSbD decision-support tools in WP5. To enable this, certain customisations of metadata, ontology alignment, and relationship structures are being implemented to optimise the way in which INSIGHT data can be semantically queried, researched, and interpreted.

4 Conclusion

D3.3 has established the technical and conceptual foundations of the INSIGHT Database, providing the central infrastructure required to manage, harmonise, and FAIRify the (meta)data produced within the project. By extending the nanoPharos platform and aligning with its ChEMBL-derived schema, the database delivers an environment capable of capturing complex information on materials, experiments, exposure and hazard studies, modelling workflows, and life-cycle sustainability indicators. Its relational structure, combined with rich metadata, provenance tracking, and semantic alignment, ensures that data entering the system are transparent, traceable, and reusable. The tools and workflows presented here support efficient data curation and structured submission from partners, offering an interface that facilitates both human interaction and machine accessibility. In doing so, the system facilitates INSIGHT's modelling activities in WP2, the impact assessment methodologies in WP4, and the decision-support tools in WP5. Subsequent deliverables will expand on data population, FAIRification, and the development of the Knowledge Graph.

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